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**IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS AND
LEGITIMATE INTERESTS OF FARMERS, FARMERS AND LAND
OWNERS**

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The demand for agricultural products is also increasing at the same time that the times are rapidly developing today. The cultivation of agricultural products, first of all the supply of the country's market after which the export to the world market is the most basic task facing agricultural enterprises. To further improve the performance of agricultural enterprises, huge works are being carried out by the state to organize the more efficient use of farms, farm plots.

The reforms carried out in the agrarian network of our republic and their implementation in practice, in particular, special attention is paid to the principles of effective use of land resources, give positive results. In this regard, the effective use of the existing irrigated and fertile lands, the maintenance, restoration and increase of their soil fertility, their protection and the provision of targeted use are considered one of the urgent tasks of today. Consistent reforms carried out by our government in agriculture, new forms of economic activity - the creation of a system of management of farms and peasants, and work on liberalization of their activities-are aimed directly at the development of the agricultural sector. Due to the change in the forms of ownership of land, the emphasis on irrigated lands, which are the source of our ring's genuine national wealth, invaluable property, sustenance, is increased, and thus material interest is achieved. Work is underway with a clear goal of agricultural reform. This resulted in a radical change in agriculture in the following years. Farms, in their essence, have become a leading force, providing for the main form of agricultural production, stable and effective

development of the industry. Most importantly, a real owner - landowner appeared in the village.

In recent years, the effective use of farm plots, consistently and clearly targeted, has been an important factor in improving the efficiency of farmers' activities. The analysis showed that it was possible to form stable farms, significantly increase their personal working capital, ensure the rational use of land and water resources, as well as mineral fertilizers, agricultural machinery and other resources, as well as more accurately organize labor, and the material and technical base of farms was strengthened.

By implementing additional measures on the use of land plots on farms, they are aimed at further improving the efficiency of their activities, impartial and transparent selection of farmers, as rightful owners of land, rational use of land and other resources on this basis, increasing future productivity and increasing the volume of production of agricultural products, improving the financial situation of, Work was carried out with the Working Groups at the sites on an in-depth analysis of production, economic and financial indicators of farms operating in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regions, as well as on bringing their land areas to their optimal volumes, and work was completed to optimize (optimize) the dimensions of land plots on farms. The total number of farms as of 1 January 2016 was 100,716, including specialty: cotton-growing 48,401, wheat 8,805, livestock 6,965, horticulture 20,679, viticulture 3,097, vegetable-growing 7,114, tobacco 2,417, and 3,238 in the other direction.

The decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev Shavkat Miromonovich "on measures to protect the rights and legitimate interests of farmers, farmers and land owners, to radically improve the system of effective use of agricultural fields", adopted on October 9, 2017, opened the door of great opportunities for the further development of the agricultural system, cannot be exaggerated. The decree laid out priorities aimed at protecting the rights and

legitimate interests of farmers, farmers and landlords and improving the efficiency of their use of land plots.

In addition, the further development of the activities of farmers, farmers and tomarka landowners to create an effective ridge of protection of their rights and legitimate interests, especially touched on the issues of improving the regulatory legal framework in this Soha. In addition, the decree also spoke about the establishment of multi-sector farms, the radical improvement of their activities and the effective use of land on multi-sector farms in yanda. Yani: the proposal of the commission for the further development of economic reforms in agriculture on the mountain of gradual transformation of farms into multi - sector farms in 2018-2021 was approved, and since January 1, 2022, it is established that land lease agreements with farms that have not established multi-sector activities will be canceled in accordance with the legislation.

Our countryman : "tomorrow is an additional source of income !", they also argued that the slogan should be widely promoted among the villagers and absorbed into the daily lives of the landowners in the decree. Another joyous aspect of this decree: the badges of “ Advanced farmer” , “hard worker farmer“, and “Namunali tomarqachi” were established, which were awarded to farmers and landowners who made a worthy contribution to the growth of agricultural culture and achieved high results in production.

In conclusion, this decree serves to protect the rights and legitimate interests of farmers, farmers and landlords, to further radically improve the system of effective use of agricultural arable land, to increase the cultivation and realization of agricultural products, and has opened a wide way to bring reforms in this direction to a new level. The development of the country's agriculture leads to an increase in agricultural production. And the increase in agricultural products is a guarantee that the people will live happily ever after. Therefore, the organization of more efficient use of land areas by farmers, farmers and land owners is one of the pressing issues of today. For the effective use of land, however, the most important

thing is to hand it over to a worthy owner. Protecting the rights and legitimate interests of farmers, farmers and land owners, radical improvement of the system of effective use of agricultural arable land leads not only to the development of agriculture, but also to the development of the country's economy.

The Earth will feed you if you feed the Earth.

Literature used:

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